

Self-Discovery of Robot Body Morphology: An Unsupervised Graph-Based Framework

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Abstract

Conventional kinematic modeling often relies on prior knowledge of the robot model, which limits applicability to complex or soft robotic systems. Morphological identification [1] and the estimation of kinematic parameters are fundamental prerequisites for the effective control of complex robotic systems, particularly anthropomorphic robots characterized by kinematic redundancy and intricate mechanisms such as gimbal wrists [2]. This research presents a model-free approach for the autonomous discovery of robot structure using solely unlabeled marker data obtained from a motion capture system, without any prior knowledge of the robot's kinematic model.

The proposed methodology initiates with a motor babbling phase lasting two minutes to induce relative motion among markers (Fig. 1a). The resulting trajectory data is utilized to construct a connectivity graph (Fig. 1b), where the statistical variance of pairwise distances serves as a criterion to cluster markers into distinct rigid bodies (Fig. 1c). Subsequently, analyze the graph's structure and reorder the connectivity matrix (Fig. 1d).

Following structural inference, the system proceeds to Geometric Parameter Recovery. The base link is first identified as the component exhibiting the lowest spatial variance. A Minimum Spanning Tree (MST) is then constructed using Prim's algorithm to establish the correct parent-child relationships between links (Fig. 1e). Local coordinate frames for each link are initialized via Principal Component Analysis (PCA). Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) and circle fitting optimization are integrated to precisely estimate the joint axes of rotation and pivot positions (Fig. 1f). This process yields a complete kinematic model (Θ) (Fig. 1g).

Experimental validation was conducted using a 7-DOF Kinova manipulator in Ignition Gazebo. The entire pipeline, from graph construction to parameter recovery, requires approximately 60 seconds on

a standard PC (i7-12700h). The results demonstrate the system’s capability to accurately identify the morphology of serial manipulators with revolute joints and to reconstruct their kinematic equations. The proposed method successfully recovered the robot kinematics with a mean absolute error (MAE) of 37.44 mm, Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) 40.72 mm, Standard Deviation (SD) 16.00 mm, maximum error 70.94 mm corresponding to a relative error of 1.15% with respect to the 3.2 meter workspace diagonal.

Moreover, the graph-based connectivity inference is robust to temporary marker occlusions (incomplete data), as the topological structure persists as long as the overall connectivity remains intact over the aggregation period

The proposed framework is inherently scalable to complex morphologies, including walking robots, as the graph-based Minimum Spanning Tree (MST) naturally accommodates branching kinematic chains. While this study focuses on revolute joints, the method is extensible: prismatic joints can be identified by analyzing linear distance variance during clustering, and spherical joints can be modeled as three intersecting revolute axes.

Furthermore, the applicability of this framework extends to understanding biological systems (e.g., enabling non-invasive identification of human joint centers) and to obtaining exact kinematic models of soft robotics where the parameters in constrained by manufacturing uncertainties and material deformations. Current research focused on extending this framework to address more complex joint configurations, such as modeling of anthropomorphic wrist joints [3].

Figure 1: Pipeline visualization. (a) 7-DOF Kinova with markers. (b) Raw rigidity matrix of permuted data. (c) Block-diagonal clusters after Rigid Body Clustering. (d) Adjacency matrix reordered by Topological Inference. (e) Extracted MST kinematic tree. (f) Estimated joint axes ($w_1 - w_7$) and pivots via Geometric Parameter Recovery. (g) Final reconstructed robot description (Θ).

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